

SOCIAL NETWORKING AND ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT IN AKWA IBOM STATE

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ABSTRACT

Social networking site are fast becoming very popular means of interpersonal and public communication in the society. It is the fastest growing sector that contributes immensely to economic development of any nation. Hence, the economic potentials of the social network would translate to economic success for Akwa Ibom State only to the extent social network has penetrated the population. However, social network site has led to the degradation of our moral values. People now use the platform to engage in all sort of immoral activities. It has also led to a sharp increase in crime rate in Akwa Ibom State. People are constantly duped, kidnapped or even killed by social media-accentuated means. After due study, analysis and findings, the study recommended that for effective crime control to take place, there is the need to established a coalition of key agencies such as schools, job creation and effective law enforcement agencies as way of preparing and mobilizing young people for harnessing social network and economic potentials that would lead to socio-economic development in Nigeria.

Keywords: Social Networking, Communication, and Economic Development

INTRODUCTION

Social network is a social networking service. It is an online platform that people use to build social nets or social relations with people who share similar personal or career interest, background or real life connections. The internet is a large system of connected computers around the world which allows people to share information and communicate with one another using e-mail. It serves as a veritable tool for research. The usage of internet advanced from sharing of information via e-mail to social network sites. Social network sites were created to make friends and stay in touch with one's family members that are away.

It is, however, obvious that social networking sites are fast becoming very popular means of both interpersonal and public communication in Nigeria. They serve as modern interactive communication channels through which people connect to one another, share

ideas, experiences, pictures, messages and information of interest. Anim (2007) defines social networking sites import as we based services that allow individuals to construct a public or semi-public profile within a bounded system; articulate a list of other users with whom they share a connection and view and traverse their list of connection and those made by others within the system.

Awake (2011) argues that 'Social networking' has become hugely popular. This is because it took 38 years for radio to reach 50 million users; 13 years for television to attract the same number and 4 years for the years for the internet to do so, but it took facebook 12 months only to gain 200 million users. Social networking sites provide various interactive platforms based on the intensions of their founders. There are for instance, social, political, academic, business, sports, romantic and religious platforms. In other words, the social networking site by its nature has the capabilities of educating, informing, entertaining and inflaming the audience.

Evidence has shown that social networking sites have become 'widespread tool for communication and exchange of ideas; helping individuals and organizations to reach a phenomenally vast audience that could hitherto not be reached by traditional media". Thus since inception, social networking sites like facebook, twitter, 2go, My Space, Sykpe and so on, have connected millions of users, many of whom have made use of these sites in all their daily activities (Onomo, 2012). These activities vary from economic, social, political and even religious activities. Indeed, social network plays significant role in the development discourse of the contemporary world.

Florunso (2010) has observed that in Africa, social networking sites are becoming widespread than it has ever been before and it appears that people's perception of this technology is diverse. Similarly, Essoungou (2010) explains that the new communication technology is one of the few ways that young Africans can bypass the inefficiency in the system that allow the status quo to hold on. It lowers the barriers to entry for everyone to get involved and be heard. This is because the disposition of people of a given community could shape the media in existence there. A cerebral media scholar Anim (2007), aptly notes that societies greatly influence the operations and functions of the media that operate within those societies. The manner in which the social networking were used and the role they play in the recent uprising which rocked the middle-East popularly referred to as "Arab Spring" could be deciphered as credence to the above academic observations.

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

Over the years, social networking sites have metamorphosed from few-user-based sites into phenomena that have become riches for billions of users. By definition, social network could be described as an online platform that focuses on facilitating and building social relationship among people who share the same interest, activity, views or perceptions. Examples of social network is social media which include: Facebook, Twitter, Skype, WhatsApp, BB chat, galaxy chat, 2go among others

It is a known fact that every coin ha two side. That means, social network has both negative as well as positive effects on Nigerians. Indeed, it is very hard for us to know or detect the percentage of how our lives have been changed completely by the effects of social network, until we compared to what obtained some years ago. In recent years, social network likely more than anything else, have devastated effects on most of our daily lives.

The negative effect of social media are vast. Some of its effects include: time wastage, health effect, religious effect, serious accidents on our major roads, wrong way of earning money fraudulently, waste of resources, decrease in productivity, it reduces learning and research capabilities of students and other researchers, reduces useful command of the mechanics of the English language, effects on writing skills, menace of examination malpractice, misunderstanding between two or more mutual friends, inefficiency, immorality and other forms of criminal activities perpetrated in the society today (Oduche, 2013).

People who are addicted to social networking are vulnerable to higher risk factors in life, resulting from exposure to technology aided innovations and inventions, embedded in social networking which facilitate easy connections among people over space and time. Social network sites have become perilous as a result of the activities of criminals. Studies have shown that there seems to be a positive correlation between the usages of social media with cyber bellying. Social media have led to a sharp increase in crime rate in Akwa Ibom State. People are constantly duped, kidnapped or even killed by social media-accentuated means.

Also, our moral values have been degraded occasioned by social network as people now use the platform to engage in all sorts of immoral activities. Similarly, people do not have privacy again as security agencies have access to people's personal accounts which compromises their privacy. An individual never know when he/she is visited by any investigation officer regarding any issue that he or she mistakenly or unknowingly discussed over the internet.

Also, the reading habits of scholars in the various fields of study and the general public have been washed down the drain as a result of the emergence of technology and advent of social network. Reading is the essential factor that forms the foundation of greatness in everyone's life irrespective of gender, status and age. It helps to develop an individual and is also important when trying to pass an examination. One of the major reasons for the dwindling rate at which students / academic and the general reading public are facing is due to the introduction of phones, computers, and the wrong usage of all forms of communication technology. Social media and their networks such as BBM, WhatsApp, Instagram, 2go, Facebook, Twitter, Badoo, YouTube and the use of Internet as a whole have been the major obsessions of most Akwa Ibom State citizens and this has contributed negatively to economic development of the state. This is because, the social scientist, for instance, who is to find solutions to the societal problems based on their profession can no longer carry out effective research on some critical issues bordering on the socio-political and economic development of the society because of the social network. Scholars in various fields of human endeavours now carry out "copy and paste" research which has little or no impact on the socio-economic development of the state.

However, despite the negative effects of social network discussed-above some positive contributions have been noticed in the socio-economic development of Akwa Ibom State. Also, our social lives help in socializing and building up confidence in the future. The use of computer and other technologies help us to develop ourselves in Web designs, artistic skills and other computer-related programs. This increases our creativity and technological know-how which have a positive impact on socio-economic development of Akwa Ibom State. It is against the background that this study seeks to examine the impact of social network on the economic development of the people of Akwa Ibom State.

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

Technological Determination Theory

The fundamental relationship between communication and development has become a well established paradigm in media studies (Ekwelie, 1999; Okunna, 2002; Baran, 2010). The relationship between the mass media and development is in turn founded on this paradigm, and this relationship necessarily extends to economic development (oyd and Nicole, 2008). It is based on this paradigm that social media could be viewed as possessing an economic dimension.

The theory of technological determination affirms this relationship in absolute terms by stating that technology is at the root of all social phenomenon including development. It is a reductionist theory which believes that humans are conditioned y technological advancements as they actualize their existence; that their actions are inevitably shaped by the nature and the extent of technological structures existing in the society at any point in time (Leonard, 2008; Baran and Davis, 2001). In other words, we are without choice and freewill as far as technology is concerned. Thus, the technological determinism perspective will view social media technologies as an irresistible force that is reshaping the dynamics of society's realm; in short determining the economic culture.

Mesch (2009) employed the Technological Determination Theory in trying to answer the question; is there any relationship that exists between advancements in technology and social change which may either be positive or negative? He was of the conclusion that technological advancement like "the internet" is an innovative force that has profound influence on children and youths, technology generates new patterns of expression, communication, and motivation.

For him, "much of what happens in electronic space is deeply inflected by the offline culture - the material practices and imaginaries that take place outside the electronic space Digital space is not exclusive conditions that sound outside the non-digital. Digital space is embedded in the larger societal, cultural, subjective, economic and imaginary constructions of life experience and the systems within which we exist and operate". On the whole, Mesch, (2009) attributed the power of change to the internet because through its constant presence and use, it has affected the culture in ways that are radically different from those of the previous generations.

METHODOLOGY

A design is used to structure the research, to show how all of the major parts of the research thesis vis-à-vis the samples or groups, measures, treatments or programs and the methods of assignment work together and attempt to address the central research questions (Ndiyo, 2005). The study adopted descriptive method to enable the researcher elicit information from a sub-set of the population. The study also relied on both primary and secondary data. The secondary sources include academic journals, texts, news bulletins, etc., while the primary sources involve the use of questionnaire.

The study was conducted in Akwa Ibom State. Akwa Ibom State is one of Nigeria's 36 States, with a population of over 5 million people. It was created on 23rd September, 1987 from the former Cross River State by the administration of General Ibrahim Babangida (Rtd). It is currently the highest oil and gas-producing state in the country. The State has 31 local government areas, while the State's capital is Uyo, with over 7,000,000 inhabitants. The main

spoken languages are Ibibio, Annang, Eket and Oron while the main ethnic groups of the State are: Ibibio, Annang, Eket, Oron and Obolo. The cultural similarity amongst the people of the state is also epitomized by folklore, songs, dances, food, beliefs and mythology.

Findings

Table 1: Demographic Characteristics of the Respondents

Characteristics	Frequency (N = 380)	Percentages (%)
<u>Sex</u>		
Male	205	53.95
Female	117	46.05
Total	380	100
<u>Age (Years)</u>		
18-22	76	20
23-27	152	40
28-32	97	25.53
32 and Above	55	14.47
Total	380	100
<u>Educational Qualification</u>		
SSCE	38	10
OND/HND	134	35.26
B.Sc.	191	50.26
M.Sc. and Above	17	4.47
Total	380	100
<u>Respondents by local government</u>		
Eket	93	24.47
Ikot Ekpene	94	24.74
Oron	96	25.26
Uyo	97	25.53
Total	380	100

Source: Field Work, 2021

In Table 1, the sex distribution of the respondents shows that [53.95%](#) of the respondents were males, while [46.05%](#) of them were females. The table also shows the age distribution of the respondents in the following order: [18-22](#) (20%), [23-27](#) (40%). [28-32](#) ([25.53](#) %) 33 and above ([14.7](#) %). Significantly, the educational qualification distribution of the respondents revealed that 38 respondents representing 10% had SSCE, [134](#) respondents representing [35.26%](#) had OND/HND, [191](#) respondents representing [50.26%](#) had [B.Sc.](#) while 17 respondents representing [4.47%](#) had MSc and other higher educational/professional qualifications. The table also reveals the percentage distribution of respondents by local government areas in the following order: Eket ([24.47](#) %), Ikot Ekpene (24.74 %), Oron ([25.26](#) %), Uyo ([25.53](#) %).

Table 2: Respondents' opinion on the relationship between social network and job creation in Akwa Ibom State.

S/N	Statement	SA	A	D	SD	Total
1.	Social network site has created job opportunities for youths in Akwa Ibom State.	202 (53.15)	98 (25.78)	34 (8.94)	46 (12.10)	380
2.	Private organizations in Akwa Ibom State have employed so many youths with social network skills.	106 (27.89)	65 (17.10)	97 (25.52)	112 (29.4)	380
3.	Social network makes job more attractive to youths in Akwa Ibom State now than before.	214 (56.31)	103 (27.10)	23 (6.05)	41 (10.78)	380
4.	Social network had helped youths to learn how to perform better job.	152 (40)	210 (55.26)	6 (1.57)	12 (3.15)	380
5.	Social network has reduced the level of unemployment in Akwa Ibom State.	44 (11.57)	26 (6.84)	96 (25.26)	214 (53.31)	380

Source: Field Work, 2021

Table 2 reveals that majority of the respondents overwhelmingly agreed that social network site has created job opportunities for youths in Akwa Ibom State. For this item, [53.15%](#) of the respondents strongly agreed, [25.78%](#) agreed, [8.94%](#) disagreed while [12.10%](#) strongly disagreed. Accordingly, for item two, [27.89%](#) of the respondents strongly agreed, [17.10%](#) agreed; [25.52%](#) disagreed; while [29.4%](#) strongly disagreed that private organizations in Akwa Ibom State have employed so many youths with social network skills. For item three. [56.31%](#) of the respondents strongly agreed, [27.10%](#) agreed, [6.05%](#) disagreed; while [10.78%](#) strongly disagreed that social network makes job more attractive to youths in Akwa Ibom State now than before. The respondents on item four agreed that social network have helped, to learn how to perform better job. Consequently, 40% of the respondents strongly agreed; [55.26%](#) agreed, [1.57%](#) disagreed while [3.15%](#) strongly disagreed. For the lost item, [11.57%](#) of the respondents strongly agreed; [6.84%](#) agreed; [25.26%](#) disagreed, while [56.31%](#) of the respondents strongly disagreed that social network has reduced the level of unemployment in Akwa Ibom State.

Table 3: Respondents' opinion on the relationship between social network and marketing and business in Akwa Ibom State.

S/N	Statement	SA	A	D	SD	Total
1.	Marketing and business are better done now on social network.	198 (52.10)	171 (42.63)	4 (2.10)	7 (1.84)	380
2.	Social network like facebook, helps to create awareness on new products.	195 (51.31)	162 (42.63)	8 (2.10)	15 (3.94)	380
3.	Social network makes marketing less expensive in business.	194 (51.05)	173 (45.52)	5 (1.31)	8 (2.10)	380
4.	Social network makes communication with both existing and potential new customers and clients easier in a business environment.	72 (45.26)	202 (53.15)	2 (0.52)	4 (1.05)	380
5.	Facebook has really served as the fastest platform for various companies to market and advertise their products to the general public and make good sales.	197 (51.84)	180 (47.36)	1 (0.26)	2 (0.26)	380

Source: Field Work 2021

Table 3 shows that [52.10%](#) of the respondents strongly agreed that, marketing and business are better done now on social network. Also, for this item, [42.63%](#) agreed; [2.10%](#) disagreed: while [1.84%](#) strongly disagreed. Accordingly, for item seven, [51.31%](#) of the respondents strongly agreed that, social network like facebook, helps to create awareness on new products. It was also observed that, [42.63%](#) of the respondents agreed, while [2.10%](#) and [3.94%](#) disagreed and strongly disagreed respectively. For item 8, [51.05%](#) of the respondents strongly agreed that social network makes marketing less expensive in business. However, [45.52%](#) of respondents also agreed on the item while [1.31%](#) disagreed and [2.10%](#) strongly disagreed on this item. On item nine, [45.26%](#) respondents strongly agreed that, social network makes communication with both existing and potential new customers and clients easier in a business environment. More so, [53.15%](#) agreed; [0.52%](#) disagreed; while [1.05%](#) strongly disagreed on this item. Finally, [51.84%](#) of the respondents strongly agreed that, Facebook have really served as the fastest platform for various companies to market and advertise their products to the general public and make good sales, but [47.36%](#) agreed: [0.26%](#) disagreed; while [0.52%](#) strongly disagreed.

Table 4: Respondents' opinion on the relationship between social network and skill acquisition in Akwa Ibom State.

S/N	Statement	SA	A	D	SD	Total
1.	Social network have engaged a lot of youths in skill acquisition programme in Akwa Ibom State.	95 (25)	76 (20)	88 (25.26)	121 (27.36)	380
2.	Youths in Akwa Ibom State have learnt various skills such as computer operation, phone repairs, internet services, etc.	197 (51.84)	174 (45.79)	2 (0.52)	7 (1.84)	380
3.	Social network has made skill acquisition training less strenuous in the 21st century.	108 (28.42)	72 (18.94)	96 (25.26)	104 (27.36)	380
4.	Akwa Ibom State youths pay much attention to social network government job.	48 (12.63)	26 (6.84)	98 (25.78)	108 (28.42)	380
5.	With social network, Akwa Ibom State government has focused more on training the youths on skill acquisition programme than government job.	63 (16.57)	32 (8.42)	174 (45.78)	233 (61.31)	380

Source: Field Work, [2021](#).

Table 4 reveals that 25% of the respondents strongly agreed that social network has engaged a lot of youths in skill acquisition programme in Akwa Ibom State. Also, for this item, 20% agreed; [23.15%](#) disagreed; while [31.84%](#) strongly disagreed. Accordingly, for item twelve, [51.84%](#) of the respondents strongly agreed that youths in Akwa Ibom State have learnt various skills such as computer, phone repairs, internet services, etc. It was also observed that [45.78%](#) of the respondents also agreed; while [0.52%](#) and [1.84%](#) disagreed and strongly disagreed respectively. For item 13, only [28.42%](#) of the respondents strongly agreed that social network has made skill acquisition training less strenuous in the 21st century. For this item, [18.94%](#) agreed; [25.26%](#) disagreed; while [27.36%](#) strongly disagreed. [12.63%](#) of the respondents strongly agreed on item 14 that, Akwa Ibom State youths pay much attention to social network than government job. More so, [6.84%](#) agreed; [25.78%](#) disagreed; while [28.42%](#) strongly disagreed on this item. Finally, [16.57%](#) of the respondents strongly agreed that, with social network, Akwa Ibom State Government has focused more on training the youths on skill acquisition programme than government job. It was also observed that [8.42%](#) of the respondents agreed; [45.78%](#) disagreed and [61.31%](#) strongly disagreed on the item.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The study found that despite some negative tendencies, social network has the potential to drive the economy of the state to achieve greater socio-economic development that would be of greater benefit to its citizens. This finding is in line with the views of Barnes ([2013](#)) which states that, an important element in social media economics is its job creation potentials. However, from the analysis, it was discovered that social network is essential to the development of the economy by building professional networks and also increasing knowledge by utilizing the information related to innovative things in social networks. This view has been supported by Parsons (1998), who observed that the interactive features of the digital online platforms such as the social media constitute a unique combination of powerful

capabilities for marketers. Barnes (2013) also affirmed the argument that through social network, marketing and collaboration are achieved among entrepreneurs in various ways. The economic potentials of the social network would translate to economic success for Akwa Ibomites only to the extent social network has penetrated the population. Without social network platforms being at the disposal of a reasonable portion of the population, realizing its economic benefits becomes a mirage. The finding is in line with the view of Akasike (2008), which affirmed that the social network possesses potentials for boosting small capital investments. Unfortunately, the truth is that till date Internet penetration in the Nigerian states including Akwa Ibom State is still poor. This would mean that the State is still hindered from fully reaping the benefits of the social network including its economic potentials for optimal development.

Technologies that provide easy access to social media and networking sites can be beyond the means of majority of Nigerian citizens. Equally, the skills required to operate these social network sites can be overwhelming and complex thereby limiting the number of people that will have access to social media networking sites. It was also discovered in the study that the advancement of high speed internet connectivity in Akwa Ibom State is limited to major urban cities as such those in the rural areas have difficulties in having broadband access.

CONCLUSION

The reality of a computer mediated age demands a shift in the ways of dealing with the society and the increasing popularity of social media, one of many outgrowths of the Internet, clearly demonstrates the reality of this new development. The rapid growth of social media activities that have been observed over the last two decades are indicative of their entry into mainstream culture and their integration into the daily lives of many people, even within developing societies such as Nigeria. Social media tools have demonstrated the capacity to allow for the participation of the public in the social mobilization effort in ways that were not possible with other means of communication. Social media lowers the costs of sensitization, participation, organization, recruitment and training of different groups for mobilization. But like any tool, social media have inherent weaknesses and strengths and their effectiveness depends on how effective civil society, government and the public use them and how accessible they are to people who know how to use them. In Nigeria, access and use of the social media is clearly limited to urban areas and the elites, with majority of the users being young and adults. This demonstrates a serious constraint in its effectiveness in reaching the large sector of Nigerians in the rural areas who are the target of most development effort.

Social media tools appear to be the latest development in building civic engagement and sensitization of the public by helping to raise and debate local issues transparently and provide a channel and encouragement for people to get involved in civic and community issues. That is why at this critical period in Nigeria, when government has set goals and targets to achieve in its development agenda, social media tools become a necessary asset to the effective realization of these set of development goals. However, the study concludes that social networking sites have created a phenomenon over the past decade and its effects are rapidly observed in our present society in the behavioural lifestyle of our youths and adult. WhatsApp followed Facebook and BBM have surfaced as the most popular among network sites and have continued to grow in popularity and usage among youths and adults. Some youths, as found in the study, are now addicted to the sites such that if they do not have access

to them daily, they feel emotionally imbalanced and unsatisfied. The advent of the social media following the popularization of the internet has marked a watershed all over the world in virtually every sphere of life especially in the area of communication, social, economic, political and even development. Considering the fact that social media have brought about a lot of positive changes in the lives of the users throughout the world in so many ways that have led to improvement, progress and development, it was hard to dwell on the negative effects, but yet it has to be done especially with the breed of youths Nigeria has today.

Finally, if we deploy social media infrastructure maximally to promote transparency and accountability Nigeria's weak institutions will be rejuvenated to place our national economy on a fast orbit of development. We can use ICT infrastructure to put government policies on the cyberspace to encourage open budgeting and to reconfigure the architecture of government to encourage zero tolerance for corruption; the citizens will insist on participating in the business of government. The people will then own the process of policy articulation and erect the building block of a system where every public office holder is accountable to the people in the spirit of true democracy which will result in the overall development of the state.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations are put forward:

1. Education curriculum in Nigeria should integrate the economic potentials of the ICTs including the social media at both the secondary and post-secondary levels.
2. As Nigeria and other developing countries pursue cooperation with their develop counterparts towards economic growth, such cooperation should equally be extended to the social network economics.
3. The policy makers which include the Akwa Ibom State Government ministries and agencies such as the Ministry of Science and Technology, Ministry of Finance, Ministry of Information and Communication among other sectors should come up with favorable internet surfing rates and e-business policies to encourage the technological adoption that would grow the SME industry.
4. Investors should focus on helping SMEs tap the potential that comes with social media through training and provision of business solutions that bridge the existing gap where many SMEs are not using social media as a result of various limitations.
5. The government should sensitized the people on the need to explore the social media the more and to discover the hidden economic potentials of the social network which could be used to their advantage and the development of the state. Social network has increase the level of awareness about skill acquisition in Akwa Ibom State.

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